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First European records of nominate Hume's Whitethroat in the Netherlands in 2014 and Finland in 2020. Written by Rinse van der Vliet, Vincent van der Spek, Peter de Knijff, Laura Kvist, Petteri Lehikoinen, Aleksi Lehikoinen & William Velmala

Summary

On 16 September 2014, Rinse van der Vliet ringed (Arnhem BC49171), photographed and collected a body-feather of a lesser whitethroat at Vrs Meijendel. Since this bird did not look like a typical nominal Lesser Whitethroat *Sylvia curruca curruca*, RvdV took more photographs than usual. When the DNA results became available, we were surprised that the mitochondrial cytochrome B (cytB) sequence of this bird matched that of Hume's Whitethroat *Sylvia althaea althaea* (hereafter nominate *althaea*). Between 8 November and 8 December 2020, a very late 'lesser whitethroat' was seen (and caught for DNA-sampling) in a city park in Lauttasaari, close to downtown Helsinki. As with the Dutch bird, the cytB sequence of this bird matched that of nominate Hume's Whitethroat.

DNA-sequencing Dutch bird

DNA-isolation from feather samples was performed using the QIAamp DNA mini and blood mini kit. Feathers were put in a 2mL tube containing 400µL ATL buffer. 10µL ProtK and 3µL DTT (1M) were added. Samples were incubated at 56°C. After 2 hours incubation, samples were checked to see whether feather pieces were still visible. If so, another 10µL ProtK and 3µL DTT (1M) was added. When after 4 hours of incubation, no feather pieces were visible, extraction was continued. If pieces were still visible the incubation was left overnight and extraction was continued by adding 400µL AL buffer, vortexing and 10 minutes incubation at 70°C. Afterwards 400µL 100% ethanol was added. The mixture was applied to the column according to step 6 of the QIAamp DNA Mini and Blood Mini Handbook Protocol: DNA Purification from Dried Blood Spots. The extraction was completed following the remainder of the steps in this protocol except for the elution which was performed with 80µL nuclease free water with a centrifuge step of 8000rpm for 2 minutes in soft mode.

PCR reaction

In order to sequence a fragment of 610 bp. of *curruca-taxa* mitochondrial cytB gene, two overlapping Monoplex PCR's were performed with an input of 2.5-5µL of DNA-extract. See Table 1 for PCR-primer sequences. The PCR-mix contained Geneamp™ 10x PCR-buffer1 (Applied biosystems), 0.2mM dNTP's (GE healthcare), 0.4pmol per primer (Table 1) and 2U AmpliTaq gold DNA polymerase (Applied biosystems) in a total volume of 50µL. PCR's were run on a GeneAmp® PCR System 9700 with the following program. 94°C for 10 min, 36 cycles of 94°C for 30 seconds, 50°C for 30 seconds and 72°C for 2 minutes ending with 72°C for 10 minutes.

PCR purification

The PCR-products were visualized using the QIAxcel. Afterwards a purification step using the QIAquick® PCR purification kit (QIAGEN) was performed according to the protocol from this kit. Elution was performed in 20-70µL Aquabrain depending on the amount of PCR-product visible on the Qiaxcel (Figure 2).

Sequencing PCR

Forward and reverse sequencing PCR's were performed using an input of 1-4µL of purified PCR-product. PCR-mix contained: 5x sequencing buffer big dye terminator V1.1 v3.1 (Life Technologies), 0.6pmol sequencing primer (tabel2) and 2µL BigDye® Terminator v3.1 ready reaction mix (Life

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Technologies) in a total volume of 10µL. Sequencing PCR's were run on a pre-heated (96°C) GeneAmp® PCR System 9700 with the following program. 96°C for 1 min, 25 cycles of 96°C for 10 seconds, 50°C for 5 seconds and 60°C for 4 minutes.

Sequencing PCR purification

12µL water was added to the sequencing PCR-product. Then the product was purified using the DyeEx® 2.0 Spin kit (QIAGEN), protocol for Dye-Terminator Removal.

Sequencing

Purified sequencing PCR-product was run on an AB3100 Genetic Analyzer.

Table1: Forward and reverse primer sequences for the CytB sequencing of *curruca* samples. Lowercase sequences tgtaaacgacggccagt and caggaaacagctatgacc are M13 tails.

Primer	Reverse primer sequence
CYTB-Curruca1_21M13-f	5'-tgtaaacgacggccagtCCCCATCCTAAAAATCGTCA-3'
CYTB-Curruca1_M13REV-r	5'caggaaacagctatgaccTAATTACGGTTGCCCTCAG-3'
CYTB-Curruca2_21M13-f	5'-tgtaaacgacggccagtGGGATCTACTACGGATCCTACC-3'
CYTB-Curruca2_M13REV-r	5'-caggaaacagctatgaccGGAGTAGTGGGGTGAATGG-3'

Table2: Overview of the forward and reverse primer sequences for the sequencing PCR

	Forward	Reverse
Sequencing PCR primers	TGTAAAACGACGGCCAGT	CAGGAAACAGCTATGACC

The resulting sequence was submitted to GenBank and released as record number MW727221.

DNA-sequencing Finnish bird

The following information was provided:

DNA was extracted using the QuickExtract buffer by Epicentre as suggested by the manufacturer. A 637 bp fragment of the mitochondrial cytochrome b gene was analysed. Amplified by PCR using primers L15004 (CCA TCC AAC ATC TCA ACT TGA TGA AA) and H15547 (AAT AGG AAG TAT CAT TCG GGG TTT GAT G, from Edwards et al. 1991). The PCR was performed in 10 µl volumes containing 20-50 ng of template DNA, 0.2 mM of each dNTP, 0.5 µM of both primers, 2 µl of reaction buffer (5X), 5 mM MgCl₂ and 0.02 U of Phusion DNA-polymerase (Thermo Scientific). The PCR profile in Piko Thermal Cycler included an initial denaturation at 98°C for 1 min 10 s followed by 40 cycles of 98°C for 1 s, 57 °C for 10 s and 72°C for 40 s and a final extension at 72°C for 1 min. PCR-product was sequenced using both primers with the BigDye Terminator v.3.1 Kit, and run on an ABI3730 (Applied Biosystems).

Network preparation and analyses

As a first step, we combined all 212 *curruca* CytB sequences published by Olsson et al. (2013) and obtained from GenBank, with those from the present study into a single fasta file. Sequences were aligned and clipped to an overlapping size of 555 bp. As a second step, we used DnaSP v6 (from <http://www.ub.edu/dnasp/>), to extract and export a polymorphic sites only file in RDF-format from this fasta file. The resulting rdf file was used to prepare a median joining network using Network 10.2 (from <https://www.fluxus-engineering.com/sharenet.htm>). The network was adjusted using Network Publisher (purchased via <https://www.fluxus-engineering.com/sharenet.htm>), and subsequently exported as an .emf file. This .emf file was edited in PowerPoint which resulted in Figure 1 below.

